

Rebuttal to “[Summary Reply](#) to ‘Discussion: Tidal variation and flow dynamics in Indian Sundarban based on field observation and numerical models’ by [Das et al. \(2025\)](#). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2025.109526>”

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Abstract

This article evaluates the *Summary Reply* of [Paul et al. \(2025\)](#) to the paper of [Das et al. \(2025\)](#), written to discuss [Paul et al. \(2024\)](#). It highlights significant methodological inconsistencies in their clarification. The use of crudely prepared bamboo poles and inadequate manpower, besides unconvincing logistical setup and missing data, diminishes the credibility of [Paul et al.’s \(2024, 2025\)](#) tidal observations. Their model-based mean sea level referencing and erratic bathymetric merging reveal conceptual confusion in datum control. Misapplication of Manning’s roughness, unverified model parameters, and data recycling for validation further question the reliability of their work. Additionally, cartographically un/misrepresented channels, inconsistent visual scales, and rhetorical arguments obscure rather than illuminate the key issues. Collectively, these deficiencies reaffirm that [Paul et al. \(2025\)](#) fail to resolve the methodological and analytical flaws of [Paul et al. \(2024\)](#), while compromising scientific transparency and reproducibility.

Keywords: Indian Sundarban, Tide monitoring, Estuarine bathymetry, MIKE 21 modelling

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1. Introduction

Paul et al. (2024, *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 304, 108851) used observed tide level data and channel bathymetry for simulating tidal hydrodynamics in the Saptamukhi, Thakuran, and Matla estuaries of the Indian Sundarban through the MIKE 21 suite. A number of issues detected in this work were pointed out in a discussion article (Das et al., 2025). We showed that (1) Paul et al.’s (2024) claim of collecting 15 days of tidal data every 20 minutes at seven remote sites is questionable due to a lack of logistical details and undiscussed data gaps. At least four of these stations were in intertidal zones, which are unlikely to record low tides. Explanations for maintaining the tide poles or referencing the collected data to common datums or mean sea level (MSL) were also not given. (2) The authors’ bathymetric map combined two datasets (NHO 301 and GEBCO) without addressing their differences in reference datum and coarse resolutions. This made the charts unsuitable for reliable estuarine depth modelling. (3) Manning’s roughness coefficient was not properly estimated in the work, and (4) the observed water levels mostly remained above MSL with no clarification provided. Further issues included (5) inconsistent data intervals and colour schemes across figures, and (6) flawed model validation using selective stations and contradictions among figures, tables, and texts. We may now examine whether, and to what extent, the authors have responded to the concerns raised in our discussion.

In a *Summary Reply* to our discussion article, Paul et al. (2025) attempted to defend their work (Paul et al., 2024) by contradicting our methodical and evidence-based criticisms. However, we found it to be a scientifically flawed clarification on several counts. Rather than constructively engaging with the substantive, evidence-based methodological issues raised by us (Das et al., 2025), the authors attempted to obscure core concerns through selective interpretation and rhetorical diversion. This compelled us to demonstrate, through the present article, that the purported explanations by Paul et al. (2025) fail scrutiny, emphasising the correctness of the criticisms put forward earlier (Das et al., 2025), exposing deeper flaws in Paul et al.’s (2024) contribution.

2. Issues raised by Paul et al. (2025) in the *Summary Reply*

2.1 Issues related to tide measurements

2.1.1 Unreliable measurement tools and techniques

The tools employed by Paul et al. (2024, 2025) for tide measurement at seven field stations are unconvincing in terms of scientific reliability and methodological accuracy. Their reliance on crude bamboo culms as tide poles represents a major compromise in precision and durability. Most pole photos of Paul et al. (2025) depict visibly curved, irregular, and uneven bamboos, calling into question their suitability for precise tidal observations. Further contradictions arise from the authors’ claim (Paul et al., 2025) of using poles measuring 5–6 m in an environment where the tidal range itself reaches up to 5.7 m (Fig. 3 of Paul et al., 2024; Fig. 4 of Das et al., 2025).

By contrast, Chatterjee et al.’s (2013) widely acclaimed earlier study on tidal measurement in the Indian Sundarban adopted a far more defensible method, employing rigid iron pipes during a three-day tidal survey in 2011, supported by clear photographic evidence. Their use of straight, durable, and dense galvanised iron pipes (specific gravity: 7.85) as poles, along with fixed gauge installations, provided a clearly more reliable

solution for estuarine tide monitoring (Fig. 1). It is therefore perplexing that Paul et al. (2024, 2025), a decade later, opted for a technologically inferior method.

Fig. 1. Instrument setup for 72-hour tidal measurement study by Chatterjee et al. (2013). (a) Reproduced Fig. A2e of Chatterjee et al. (2013), depicting a fixed tide pole secured with three iron guy-wires anchored to the bank and monitored from a motorized boat. (b) Reproduced Fig. A2h of Chatterjee et al. (2013), showing a close-up view of a tide gauge constructed from a galvanized iron pipe with clearly marked graduations, ensuring readability from a distance. (c) Reproduced Fig. A2i of Chatterjee et al. (2013), illustrating a tide pole supported by an attached stake, guy-wires, and installed within a tidal channel.

Bamboo, being an organic material with inconsistent straightness and variable diameter, is inherently incapable of meeting the accuracy requirements of calibrated tidal gauges. The specific gravity of the bamboo found in the Sundarban region (*Bambusa balcooa*) typically ranges between 0.46–0.82, and the culms are mostly hollow. It is unlikely that such makeshift poles, erected with minimal foundation and basal

support (Fig. 2b, 2c of Paul et al., 2025) can withstand strong tidal currents of ~ 1 m/s (Pitchaikani, 2020) for 15 consecutive days and would not collapse and float away. Paul et al.’s (2025, p. 2) assertion that ‘lighter poles were stabilised by direct insertion into the substrate’ was not supported by any explanation of insertion depth, hence raising doubts regarding their ability to remain vertically stable during high-energy tidal phases. Station-wise information should have been provided by the authors to differentiate where ‘lighter’ and ‘heavier’ poles were used, which would have made replication and validation feasible. Any measurement or complete photograph showing the length of the ‘heavier’ foundation stake onto which the bamboo culm was bolted was also not provided. Judging by photo 1c of Paul et al. (2024) that shows two humans, they stood at least 1.5 m above the creek beds; their total length, including the part driven into the basal sediments, must have been more. It is difficult to see how the ‘heavier poles’ were embedded and the bamboo poles bolted to these foundations in a submerged condition, since Paul et al. (2025; p. 2) stated that ‘all poles were installed below the expected LLT, based on local knowledge and our pilot survey observations’. Any shift or tilt of the base would inevitably distort tidal readings, rendering the data inaccurate. Besides this, we found that there was no standardisation in pole installations. For example, rope support by two additional logs is shown in Paul et al.’s (2025) Fig. 2c, which was not there in the other photos. Additionally, no details are provided on the duration, timing, or scope of this so-called ‘pilot survey’. If the installations relied solely on ‘local knowledge’ or brief observations, it cannot ensure accuracy over a fortnight-long tidal regime, as such reliance cannot supersede geomorphic and hydrodynamic evidence.

Fig. 2. Comparative field photographs of Station 1 (Haripur). (a) Reproduced Fig. 2c of Paul et al. (2025), showing an exposed sandflat in the surf zone beside a visibly uneven bamboo pole, the full length of which is indeterminable as the photograph did not capture it entirely. Small wooden stakes support the pole, rendering it vulnerable to lateral drag and buoyant lift during prolonged exposure. (b) Field photograph of the reported coordinate location (Paul et al., 2024: 21°36.342'N, 88°17.185'E) during spring low tide, showing the station fully exposed and the lowest low water (LLW) level hundreds of meters away, with anchored boats grounded at low tide (22 August 2024; viewing southeast).

Considering the claimed 20-minute interval readings over 15 days, often from distances of 40 m and more, it is highly unlikely that the fine markings of about 1 cm (Fig. 1a, 1b of Paul et al., 2025) could be deciphered with precision — especially at night, even with the aid of high-beam torches and binoculars. Paul et al. (2025) also did not standardise the style of pole markings. We find that the poles were painted white in some localities, and were not painted at all in some others; the colour of the markings also varied between black and green.

Curiously enough, Paul et al. (2025) did not mention date and time in any of the installed tide pole photos, making cross verification with the inundation level impossible. Moreover, in support of the ‘robustness’ of their stated methodology, all seven poles should have been photographed in the daytime low tide and high tide conditions — especially in the springs — throughout the survey period. Unfortunately, such time-series photos were not provided for any of their observatories, upholding Das et al.’s (2025) apprehensions on data integrity. It is important to note that Fig. 3d of Paul et al. (2025) shows a slanted, partially submerged bamboo pole tied to what appears to be a dead mangrove plant, indicating an intertidal location. Such installations would be exposed during low tide, preventing continuous data capture across the campaign. This casts doubt on the feasibility of obtaining uninterrupted measurements at Samsernagar (Station 7) during the reported 15-day period by Paul et al. (2024, 2025).

The above points do little to justify Paul et al.’s (2025, p. 1) claims of ‘thoughtfully crafted’ and ‘reproducible field-appropriate procedures’. In reality, their approach constitutes an assemblage of improvised techniques lacking standardisation, calibration, and adequate documentation. The discrepancies and misleading claims by Paul et al. (2025) regarding tide monitoring instruments and station locations are shown in Table 1 and Figs. 2–6.

2.1.2 Questionable data completeness and methodological omission

Das et al. (2025), in their *Discussion*, questioned the feasibility and completeness of Paul et al.’s (2024) 15-day tide monitoring across remote tidal sites, in the absence of logistical and operational details. In response, Paul et al. (2025, p. 1) attempted to justify this omission by citing ‘strict word limitations of the journal’. This appears to be a weak justification, as essential logistical details — such as pole anchoring methods and survey techniques — form the backbone of this type of scientific study and cannot be deprioritised in favour of descriptive narrative. Their omission reflects a lack of methodological transparency in their work. Paul et al. (2025, p. 2) further acknowledged that ‘in rare instances’ water levels fell below the zero mark and that 13% of observations were missing, which they interpolated ‘as per the observed rate of tidal rise and fall’. Since Paul et al. (2024, 2025) claimed that their all stations were subtidal, it is difficult to understand how an unspecified number of tide poles became exposed at low tide in ‘rare instances’. This indicates either their misunderstanding of tidal behaviour, or a flawed measurement setup. Moreover, the admission of a 13% data gap — entirely absent from the original article — reveals a significant omission that compromises data integrity. Presenting the post-hoc disclosure as a routine interpolation obscures its seriousness. Furthermore, citing a 13% missing dataset without clarifying its distribution across sites renders the statement meaningless. Was this 13% concentrated at specific stations or distributed across all sites? Did they represent the low-water end? Equally problematic is the absence of any information on how the interpolation was performed by them. The absence of even the basic information on interpolation procedures exacerbates the credibility issue. Using the reported observation frequency by Paul et al. (2024), Das et al.

(2025) estimated that the dataset should contain 7,704 readings, implying that 1,002 readings (13%) were missing — an unacceptably large gap that further underscores the irregularity of Paul et al.’s (2024) measurements.

Paul et al.’s (2025, p. 4) subsequent clarification — that the 13% data gap occurred ‘mainly during early morning and evening shift transitions’ and were corrected using ‘linear interpolation’ — deepens the aforementioned concerns. Normalising a lapse of 13% data is unacceptable as it contradicts their claim of uninterrupted tide monitoring. Also, their assertion that the presence of interpolated data ‘does not affect dataset validity’ is inaccurate, particularly if missing values include low-water readings. Most importantly, these additional clarifications emphasise the lack of transparency and fallacy in their data reporting.

2.1.3 Dubious manpower distribution and logistical inconsistencies

Paul et al.’s (2025, p. 2) assertion that ‘seventeen trained residents, including fishermen, shopkeepers, and students, were engaged in day and night shifts across seven tidal stations’ raises concerns about the feasibility of their fieldwork. This staffing level translates to only two to three individuals per site — clearly inadequate for uninterrupted 24-hour monitoring sustained over 15 consecutive days. Even under the most generous assumptions, it is far-fetched to expect such limited personnel to continuously observe the bamboo pole graduations without breaks for meals and sleep. This defies both human endurance and practical fieldwork standards. The reference to ‘day and night shifts’ further complicates the claim. How were shift rotations managed at stations staffed by only two individuals? If one rested while the other worked, independent cross-verification of measurements would be impossible, inevitably introducing observational gaps and subjectivity.

The logistical and financial claims made by Paul et al. (2025) are also questionable and strain scientific credibility. With a total budget of ₹ 110 thousand (1 US\$ = ₹ 73.93 in 2021) reportedly sourced from a fellowship program, the remuneration for field assistants would necessarily be meagre after covering the expenses of observatory setup, equipment, and transport of materials and personnel. It is doubtful whether such a small compensation can motivate field observers to maintain meticulous, round-the-clock records continuously for 15 days. Das et al. (2025), instead, compared Paul et al.’s (2024, 2025) setup to the rigorously coordinated study by Chatterjee et al. (2013), which, despite spanning only 72 hours, operated 30 monitoring stations, each staffed with six trained observers, a supervisor, and mechanized boats to ensure accurate readings. Funded by the Indian National Centre for Ocean Information Services (INCOIS) and supported by government bodies, NGOs, and security forces, the project design stood for scientific integrity and precision. In stark contrast, the manpower, timeframe, and budget claimed by Paul et al. (2025) seem too inadequate, raising concerns about the authenticity of their purported field data collection process.

2.1.4 Limitations of observational precision

Paul et al. (2025, p. 2) attempted to justify their field method by stating that observers stayed within 40 m of the bamboo poles for ‘safety and practicality’, using ‘low-range portable binoculars’ and ‘high-beam torches’ for distant and nighttime readings. This statement has little value when confronted with on-ground realities. At Jharkhali (Station 6), for instance, dense mangrove cover obstructs direct line-of-sight to the observation point from the embankment, making it impossible to read pole gradations at short distances even during the daytime (Fig. 3). Their measurement site lies ~130 m from the lowest low water (LLW) to

Fig. 3. Station 6 (Jharkhali) under varying tidal settings. (a) Reproduced Fig. 3b of Paul et al. (2025), showing a tide pole placed on an exposed mudflat beside a river. The geomorphic setting in this image does not match the landscape associated with the Station 6 coordinates provided in Paul et al. (2024). (b) Reproduced Fig. 1c1 of Das et al. (2025), displaying a Google Earth image (30 November 2021) with the reported coordinates for Station 6 (yellow placemark; Paul et al., 2024: 22°03.522'N, 88°39.572'E), located far from both the spring LLW and the embankment. Red and orange dots mark the vantage points for c and d, respectively. (c) Field photograph (20 August 2024; viewing west) showing dense mangrove vegetation blocking visibility from the embankment toward the supposed station site, with the spring high tide position marked. (d) Geotagged field photograph (20 August 2024; viewing west) depicting the vegetated mudflat with knee-deep mud at the reported ST-6 coordinates, with the spring low tide position indicated.

the east, and 120 m from the embankment to the west — distances at which human visual competence, even with the aid of binoculars and torches (illumination of which would be many times smaller than daylight), cannot achieve the precision they claim. Expecting observers to traverse knee-deep mud at night and still obtain accurate tidal readings is both logistically unrealistic and operationally unsafe. The poor legibility of the bamboo poles visible in [Paul et al.’s \(2025\)](#) photographic evidence is to be added to this problem. Notably, although the *Summary Reply* asserts that tide data from one station were omitted due to the absence of nighttime records (Fig. 3c of [Paul et al., 2025](#)), it provides no photographic proof that any nighttime monitoring was ever conducted, further weakening the credibility of their claimed procedure.

2.1.5 Dubious independent tide datasets and sampling intervals

[Paul et al. \(2024\)](#) reported tide monitoring at seven stations at 20-minute intervals over a continuous 15-day period. However, three subsequent articles from the same group documented tidal readings at 5- or 10-minute intervals, often at overlapping locations and during the same monitoring window (see Supplementary Table 1 of [Das et al., 2025](#)). [Paul et al.’s \(2025, p. 3\)](#) claim that these datasets are ‘independent’ raises serious methodological concerns. If true, this would imply either that multiple tide poles were installed side-by-side at the same sites to record at 5-, 10-, and 20-minute intervals simultaneously, or that the authors inexplicably chose a coarser 20-minute interval for their primary study despite generating higher-resolution data. Were the same team of two to three data collectors employed for these simultaneous observations also? While the high-frequency (5-minute) observations can be aggregated to lower temporal resolution (20-minute), the reverse is impossible without data manipulation. Thus, the claim of an ‘independent’ dataset suggests either an unrealistic field arrangement or selective data reporting. [Paul et al.’s \(2025, p. 3\)](#) assertion that ‘comparing them [the datasets] without context is misleading’ does little to nullify our apprehension.

2.1.6 Unjust dismissal of positional flaws and misrepresentation of station coordinates

[Das et al. \(2025\)](#) presented clear and verifiable evidence that multiple tide monitoring stations reported by [Paul et al. \(2024\)](#) were inaccurately located and unsuitable for data collection. Rather than addressing this substantive issue, [Paul et al. \(2025\)](#) attempted to downplay it in their *Summary Reply*. They labelled the demonstrably incorrect coordinates at four stations (five in reality; see Table 1 in [Das et al., 2025](#)) as ‘alleged inaccuracies’ (p. 3) and attributed them to ‘misunderstanding’ (p. 4). These phrases are scientifically misleading; [Das et al. \(2025\)](#) never ‘alleged’ inconsistencies — they actually quantified them using the coordinates published by [Paul et al. \(2024\)](#) themselves. The *Summary Reply* seeks to trivialise what is, in fact, a fundamental methodological breach. [Paul et al. \(2025, p. 4\)](#) further conceded that the coordinates ‘did not always mark the exact pole base’ because they were recorded later by the first author of [Paul et al. \(2024\)](#), ‘sometimes under high water’. This exposes a vital flaw in their field design and execution. When six of the seven stations exhibit coordinate mismatch, it does not remain a minor oversight but a systemic failure in spatial data collection and documentation that would have gone undetected if [Das et al. \(2025\)](#) had not identified them (Table 1). The identified discrepancies were not speculative. When plotted on Google Earth, several stations reported across [Paul et al. \(2024\)](#) fall within village orchards, ponds, or supratidal areas — places where tidal water cannot physically reach (see Supplementary Table 1 and KML file of [Das et al., 2025](#)). For example, Sitarampur (Station 2), according to the coordinates reported in [Paul et al. \(2024\)](#),

Fig. 4. Station 2 (Sitarampur) under different tidal conditions. (a) Google Earth image (08 January 2022) showing the originally reported Station 2 coordinates (yellow placemark; Paul et al., 2024: 21°38.249'N, 88°25.522'E), the near low tide position on 24 November 2024, and the sluice-fed channel linked to the estuary. Paul et al. (2025) conceded that the tide pole was not installed at the originally reported location; instead, it had been placed within the drainage channel, ~75 m away from the earlier reported position (red placemark), as shown in their Fig. 2a. (b) Reproduced Fig. 2b of Paul et al. (2025), showing a coastal indentation that cannot be construed as a channel with ‘unhindered tidal inflow’ based on the photographic perspective. The bent bamboo pole marks the new tide pole position asserted by Paul et al. (2025). (c) The near low tide photograph of 24 November 2024 at 11:10 (viewing southwest) showing the shallow drainage connecting the sluice gate to the estuarine front. Water draining toward the low tide level (depth: ~15 cm) shows the intertidal setting of the relocated ST-2 of Paul et al. (2025). The red placemark denotes the relocated tide pole position declared by Paul et al. (2025) which is above the low water level.

is mapped within a supratidal village orchard. In their *Summary Reply*, Paul et al. (2025, p. 4) attempted to rebut this by asserting that this station was located ‘at the mouth of a coastal indentation with unhindered tidal inflow’. In reality, neither Das et al. (2025) nor any other readers could have inferred the exact positions of the monitoring stations unless Paul et al. (2024) themselves had published the coordinates in their Table 1. More troubling is the retrospective relocation of the same tide pole position by Paul et al. (2025) to a site ~75 m away from their originally published coordinates (see Fig. 2a in Paul et al., 2025). By doing so, they have validated the very critique raised by Das et al. (2025), as this positional shift directly exposes the inaccuracy of their documentation (Table 1 and Fig. 4). This spatial relocation reveals a clear disregard for basic site-validation protocols and reinforces the argument that the station coordinates were not field-verified, but instead positioned arbitrarily on a zoomed-out map to create a superficial alignment along riverbanks, rather than reflecting genuine GPS-based measurements.

Fig. 5. Contradictory tide pole positions at Stations 4 (Paschim Sripatinagar) and 5 (Baikunthapur), as presented in Paul et al. (2024, 2025). (a1) Reproduced Fig. 2d of Paul et al. (2025), showing an uneven bamboo pole with faint graduation marks at Station 4, positioned beside a concrete jetty stairway that remains largely exposed at low tide. (a2) Google Earth image (08 January 2022) showing the reported coordinates (yellow placemark; Paul et al., 2024: 21°47.987'N, 88°28.083'E) and the probable pole location in Paul et al. (2025) (red placemark), revealing a ~25 m mismatch. (b1) Reproduced Fig. 3a of Paul et al. (2025), showing the tide pole beside a tidally exposed brick-paved jetty at Station 5. (b2) Google Earth image (13 December 2021) showing the reported coordinates (yellow placemark; Paul et al., 2024: 21°53.750'N, 88°30.257'E) and the pole position implied in Paul et al. (2025) (red placemark), indicating an ~80 m offset.

Fig. 6. Physical setting of Station 7 (Samsernagar). (a) Reproduced Fig. 3d from Paul et al. (2025), depicting a slanted tide pole fixed to a dead mangrove tree, implying an intertidal setting. The exposed bricks and structures in the lower frame suggest that the site lies adjacent to the riverbank. However, as shown in (b–d), the coordinates reported by Paul et al. (2024) place the station ~95 m from the nearest bankline, making the photograph contextually unreliable and generic enough to resemble any similar estuarine site. (b) Reproduced Fig. 1d1 of Das et al. (2025), showing a Google Earth image (27 November 2021) with the reported station position (yellow placemark; Paul et al., 2024: 22°11.742'N, 88°04.102'E) located within the intertidal zone and substantially away from the bank. Red and orange dots mark the vantage points for c and d, respectively. (c) Geotagged field photograph (01 December 2024; viewing south) showing exposed mudflat during spring low tide at the reported ST-7 coordinates. (d) Field photograph (01 December 2024; viewing east) of the ST-7 location from the bank, along with the India–Bangladesh border region.

Table 1. Discrepancies in the reported tide monitoring station locations, their claimed suitability, and the photographic evidence presented by Paul et al. (2025)

Station ID	Station	Coordinates given in Table 1 of Paul et al. (2024)	Tide monitoring suitability, as depicted in Table 1 of Das et al. (2025)	Responses given in the Summary Reply by Paul et al. (2025)	Remarks on the responses of Paul et al. (2025)
1	Haripur	21°36.342'N, 88°17.185'E	Intertidal location, not suitable	Fig. 2c: ‘ST-1 tide pole installed below the LTL’	Tide pole at ST-1 would have been exposed during spring low tide, contradicting the claim of installation 'below the LTL'. The uneven pole, propped by small wooden stakes, is susceptible to lateral drag and buoyant lift (Fig. 2a). The field photograph shows the lowest low water (LLW) level several hundred metres channelward (Fig. 2b).
2	Sitarampur	21°38.249'N, 88°25.522'E	Supratidal location, not suitable	‘Claims that poles were in “village orchards” or “supratidal” zones (e.g., ST-2: Sitarampur) are incorrect’ (p. 4)	The coordinates reported by Paul et al. (2024) plots the station in a supratidal village orchard, as seen on the Google Earth repository.
				Fig. 2a: ‘Satellite imagery showing the actual position of the ST-2 tide pole compared with coordinates reported in Paul et al. (2024a)’	In Paul et al. (2025), the tide pole location is shifted ~75 m toward an outflow channel (their Fig. 2a–b), directly reinforcing the critique of positional inaccuracy (Fig. 4a–b). This relocation effectively confirms that the original coordinates were not GPS-verified from the field site, but appear to have been arbitrarily positioned on the map.
				Fig. 2b: ‘ST-2 tide pole positioned at a coastal indentation adjacent to an open channel’	Additionally, the outflow channel is connected to a sluice gate that drains excess water from the land and can operate even outside tidal periods (Fig. 4a, 4c). The ripples observed in the flow reflect the presence of antidunes — a bedform not associated with strong tidal currents (Fig. 4c).
3	Ramganga	21°47.629'N, 88°22.689'E	Below LLW level, suitable	—	—
4	Paschim Sripatinagar	21°47.987'N, 88°28.083'E	Below LLW level, suitable	Fig. 2d: ‘ST-4 tide pole situated near a concrete jetty’	Paul et al. (2025) showed an uneven bamboo pole beside a tidally exposed jetty stairway (Fig. 5a1). However, this photographed location lies ~25 m from the coordinates reported in Paul et al. (2024) (Fig. 5a2), highlighting inconsistencies in spatial documentation.
5	Baikunthapur	21°53.750'N, 88°30.257'E	Intertidal location, not suitable	Fig. 3a: ‘ST-5 tide pole placed adjacent to a concrete jetty’	Paul et al.’s (2025) tide pole photograph beside a paved jetty (Fig. 5b1) does not match the coordinates reported in Paul et al. (2024). The reported point lies ~80 m from the photographed site, indicating the pole was not installed at the given location (Fig. 5b2).
6	Jharkhali	22°03.522'N, 88°39.572'E	Intertidal location, not suitable	Fig. 3b: ‘ST-6 tide pole positioned below the LTL’	The reported coordinates by Paul et al. (2024) place ST-6 in a physically unsuitable and inaccessible site for precise visual tide readings: ~120 m from the embankment and ~130 m from the actual LLW, with dense mangroves blocking visibility (Fig. 3). Such distances, intertidal setting, obstructed sight lines, and knee-deep mud make manual observation impossible. Furthermore, Paul et al. (2025) did not mark the ‘LTL’ (their Fig. 3b), and their tide pole location does not match the actual landscape at the reported ST-6 location.
7	Samsernagar	22°11.742'N, 89°04.102'E	Intertidal location, not suitable	Fig. 3d: ‘ST-7 tide pole fixed to a partially submerged tree below the LTL’	Paul et al.’s (2025) photograph shows the pole tied to a partially submerged mangrove tree in an intertidal site, indicating that both the pole and tree base would be exposed at low tide, making continuous 24-hour observation impossible (Fig. 6a). Compounding this, they did not mark the ‘LTL’, and the reported coordinates of Paul et al. (2024) place the pole on an intertidal mudflat ~95 m from the bankline, where no such tree could be found within a 25 m radius, rendering the photograph's unreliability (Fig. 6b–c).

Paul et al.’s (2025, p. 4) claim that ‘this positional discrepancy does not affect data quality, since all poles were installed below LLT to capture full spring–neap cycle’ is both unconvincing and self-contradictory, as the authors themselves admitted about ‘water levels dipped below the zero mark’ (p. 2). Moreover, poles placed below lowest low tide (LLT) cannot logically appear in intertidal or supratidal settings, yet their published coordinates place several stations in such zones (see Supplementary Table 1 and KML file of Das et al., 2025). Their photographic ‘evidence’ also lacks credibility: no GPS metadata is provided, and the near-identical landscape features across sites — vegetation, banklines, and jetty structures — allow easy substitution between locations. As already shown, Station 7 at Samsernagar, at the base of a mangrove that can only grow in intertidal locations (Fig. 3d of Paul et al., 2025; Fig. 6a), validate the compromises made on data integrity. Together, these issues corroborate substantial disregard for methodological precision and spatial accountability.

2.1.7 Misrepresentation of tidal referencing and mean sea level (MSL) adjustment

Notwithstanding their Fig. 3d, Paul et al. (2025) asserted that all their tide poles ‘ensured full tidal immersion’ (p. 4) and that observations were ‘adjusted to MSL’ (p. 5) using a model-based approach. Yet their explanation lacks methodological credibility and conflicts with their own data, as their depicted tidal curves never drop below zero during neap conditions (see Fig. 3 in Paul et al., 2024; reproduced as Fig. 4a in Das et al., 2025). Had a genuine MSL correction been applied, negative values would have appeared at the lower limb of the tidal cycle. This clearly indicates that no valid MSL referencing was performed. Furthermore, their approach relies on coarse global tide models, which cannot resolve the fine-scale estuarine dynamics of the Sundarban, thereby introducing systematic range distortions rather than corrections. Critically, their statement that ‘the lowest modelled water level at each station’ (p. 5) served as the baseline implies different MSL references for different stations — a direct violation of fundamental standards for comparative tidal analysis, especially when the monitoring stations are spatially distributed over a wide (120 km) and hydrodynamically interconnected system such as the Indian Sundarban.

Paul et al.’s (2025, p. 5) statement that their method was ‘less precise’ but a ‘practical and consistent solution under the field constraints’ cannot have any scientific justification. For the adjustment to MSL, at least one station must be referenced to a recognised benchmark or a known tidal datum, after which the remaining stations may be aligned accordingly through computation. Without field survey or prolonged GNSS measurements, such calibration is not possible. Finally, Paul et al.’s (2025, p. 5) statement that ‘data were adjusted to MSL to avoid confusion with the final model simulations’ helps little in understanding how this parameter — extremely critical for the study — was extracted. It represents a serious lapse in data and methodological transparency, revealing that the reported MSL referencing of the tide levels in Paul et al. (2024, 2025) was neither performed scientifically nor is it verifiable.

2.1.8 Mislabelling channel names

Paul et al. (2025) acknowledged the mislabelling of multiple channels and claimed to have updated their records accordingly. This assertion, however, exposes a fundamental flaw in the understanding of geographic and hydrological systems of their study area. Channel names in estuarine regions are unique identifiers tied to distinct tidal courses and flow regimes. Misidentifying one channel for another is not a ‘minor’ cartographic lapse, as suggested by them (Paul et al., 2025; p. 5). It basically compromises the

validity of tidal observations, model calibration, and subsequent interpretation. The erroneous labelling of a major estuarine channel as an interior distributary — or vice versa — would result in misrepresentation of tidal amplitude, current dynamics, and channel hydraulics (Das et al., 2025). Such mislabelling reflects either carelessness in data curation or a lack of understanding of the estuarine geography.

2.2 Issues related to tidal harmonic analysis and hydrodynamic modelling frameworks

Paul et al.’s (2025) *Summary Reply* reaffirms the vagueness, selective interpretation, and weak technical justification evident in Paul et al. (2024). Their reference to using the MIKE 21 World Tide Dataset Toolbox with ‘internal calibration’ (p. 5) is scientifically unsubstantiated, as they provide no information on what was calibrated, how it was conducted, or which observational data were used for validation. Invoking random phrases such as ‘globally validated methods’ cannot replace transparent reporting of parameterisation and calibration; instead, it highlights the absence of a valid scientific framework. Similarly, their claim of deliberately selecting least-squares harmonic analysis and a Rayleigh criterion of 1.0 remains unsupported, with no quantitative evidence demonstrating that these settings adequately resolved key tidal constituents. The recurring defence of ‘space limitations’ is untenable when the omitted details constitute the analytical foundation of the study.

The confusion between the Chezy coefficient and Manning’s ‘M’ is not a mere ‘misunderstanding’ by Das et al. (2025), as Paul et al. (2025) have suggested. Paul et al. (2024) explicitly mentioned the Chezy coefficient in the model description. Yet, the subsequent claim by Paul et al. (2025) that Manning’s ‘M’ is ‘implemented’, exposes an internal contradiction in the methodological coherence of their work. These parameters are not interchangeable — they derive from different empirical foundations, apply to distinct hydraulic contexts, and require separate calibration strategies. The attempt by Paul et al. (2025, p. 5) to argue that ‘both were correctly addressed in the paper’ is a post-hoc effort to reconcile contradictory statements. Crucially, Paul et al. (2025) entirely avoided engaging with the central issue — that Manning’s formulation, designed for steady open-channel flow, is inappropriate for the nonlinear, bidirectional, and tidally dominated estuarine environment of the Indian Sundarban (see Section 2.4). The authors’ reliance on self-validating terms such as ‘standard practice’, ‘internal calibration’, and ‘globally validated methods’ is symptomatic of an unverified modelling workflow.

2.3 Issues related to bathymetry setup

2.3.1 Methodological lapses related to the inappropriate use of NHO and GEBCO data

Paul et al.’s (2025) defence of their MIKE 21 bathymetry configuration reveals methodological weaknesses more serious than the alleged ‘misinterpretations’ attributed to Das et al. (2025). Their *Summary Reply* selectively rephrases the critique, while side-stepping from its core concern that the bathymetry depicted in Fig. 2a of Paul et al. (2024) does not align with the National Hydrographic Office (NHO) Chart No. 301, or the General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans (GEBCO) dataset on which their hydrodynamic reliability depends. Paul et al. (2025, p. 5) argued that the 450-m GEBCO grids are ‘widely used’ in data-scarce regions. However, their model domain is not an oceanic basin, but a finely undulating morphodynamically complex estuarine system where sub-kilometre depth variability governs tidal propagation, and flow asymmetry — a limitation already documented by Das et al. (2025). The very studies cited by Paul et al. (2025) did not rely solely on the GEBCO data; rather, they emphasised the need for

custom high-resolution bathymetry to achieve hydrodynamic realism. For example, [Dye et al. \(2019\)](#) used GEBCO only for offshore boundary extension (~80 km), not for estuarine interiors, while [Ndom et al. \(2025\)](#) found the inadequacy of even 200-m resolution data for representing underwater morphology in the Casamance Estuary, Senegal. These highlight that GEBCO’s much coarser resolution is unsuitable for estuarine hydrodynamics — a fundamental constraint [Paul et al. \(2025\)](#) ignored. Their further claim that ‘GEBCO was used only for a limited stretch along the Matla River’ (p. 5) is disproved by their own figures (Fig. 2a of [Paul et al., 2024](#); Fig. 4 of [Paul et al., 2025](#)), which show that GEBCO occupies a much broader zone beyond the NHO isobath extent (Fig. 7). The seamless contour transitions across NHO- and GEBCO-derived bathymetry in [Paul et al.’s \(2024, 2025\)](#) maps expose the very integration they denied.

[Paul et al.’s \(2025, p. 5\)](#) statement that ‘The critique that GEBCO falsely treats these creeks as land is irrelevant’ is incorrect for several reasons. First, they failed to clearly delineate the land-water boundary; their boundary outlines appear too coarse and cartographically imprecise (Fig. 2a of [Paul et al., 2024](#); Fig. 4 of [Paul et al., 2025](#)). In contrast, Fig. 2b-d of [Das et al. \(2025\)](#) clearly established the actual shoreline configuration. Next, [Paul et al. \(2024\)](#) did not specify the year of the GEBCO dataset employed. Since their field survey was conducted in 2021, [Das et al. \(2025\)](#) logically applied the GEBCO-2021 dataset, which precisely reproduced the bathymetry of the Matla Estuary and its adjoining medium- to small-sized tidal creeks shown in the original article (Fig. 2b of [Das et al., 2025](#)). This evidence directly refutes [Paul et al.’s \(2025, p. 5\)](#) statement that GEBCO was used for ‘a limited stretch along the Matla River’, and was not applied for ‘small tidal creeks’. This further erodes the authenticity of the bathymetric surface presented in [Paul et al. \(2024, 2025\)](#). Furthermore, the GEBCO bathymetry is referenced to the global WGS-84 datum, whereas [Paul et al. \(2024\)](#) made no vertical adjustment to local MSL before merging it with the NHO data. Due to its inherent data characteristics, the GEBCO-2021 surface assigns positive elevation values to many estuarine channels of the Sundarban, causing these tidal water bodies to be colour-coded as land (Fig. 3a, S1 of [Das et al., 2025](#)). This is precisely why GEBCO is unfit for fine-scale estuarine modelling in the Sundarban, as thoroughly explained by [Das et al. \(2025\)](#). Additionally, [Das et al. \(2025\)](#) highlighted that the NHO Chart No. 301 soundings were integrated into the model without any correction, rendering the middle and western section of [Paul et al.’s \(2024\)](#) bathymetry erroneous and incompatible with the GEBCO segment in the east.

[Paul et al.’s \(2025\)](#) interpretation of [Das et al.’s \(2025\)](#) bathymetric comparisons reflects a profound misunderstanding of the latter’s analytical intent. [Das et al. \(2025\)](#), in their Fig. 3, did not attempt to ‘compare’ datasets to assess their similarity; rather, they illustrated the magnitude of deviation between satellite-derived grids and field-measured echosounder profiles to show why both NHO and GEBCO data are unfit for estuarine-scale modelling in the Sundarban due to their extreme generalisation of bathymetry. By portraying this as a ‘misleading’ comparison, [Paul et al. \(2025\)](#) constructed a false narrative to deflect from their own methodological lapse — merging datasets with mismatched datums and resolutions. Besides, their claim that ‘GEBCO overestimates depths by ~7 m in small channels, a limitation acknowledged by the commenters’ (p. 5) is a distorted representation. [Das et al. \(2025\)](#) did not acknowledge this as a minor flaw — they demonstrated that the coarse GEBCO grid (~450 m) fails to represent the estuarine bathymetry adequately. Our point was and still is that [Paul et al.’s \(2024\)](#) work was based on a bathymetric dataset unsuitable for the study they attempted, and this introduced errors into their simulation. Why attempt a work for which no suitable dataset exists?

Fig. 7. Evidence of inconsistent and selectively presented bathymetry in Paul et al. (2024, 2025). (a) Paul et al.’s (2024) Fig. 2a, reproduced exactly as published; (b) Das et al.’s (2025) Fig. 2a, which verbatim replicates Paul et al.’s (2024) Fig. 2a and explicitly demarcates the boundary between the isobaths taken from NHO Chart No. 301 without any datum adjustment (left) and GEBCO data (right) using a dashed magenta line, highlighting the unacknowledged merging of two datasets of incompatible vertical references; and (c) Reproduced Fig. 4 of Paul et al. (2025), illustrating their now-claimed eastern limit of the NHO Chart used in Paul et al. (2024) by a dashed magenta zigzag line, which conspicuously mirrors the boundary demarcation presented in Das et al. (2025) for the open estuary.

2.3.2 Datum confusion and inconsistent vertical referencing

Paul et al. (2025, p. 5) clarified that ‘all bathymetric values used in the study were converted from Chart Datum (3 m below MSL) to MSL during pre-processing, as required for MIKE 21 modelling with MSL-referenced tidal boundaries’, while simultaneously admitting that ‘Fig. 2a in Paul et al. (2024) showed the original contours without vertical adjustment’. This self-contradiction cannot be nonchalantly dismissed as a ‘graphical oversight’ when the unadjusted dataset forms the very basis of their model bathymetry and mesh generation (Section 2.3.3 of Paul et al., 2024). In MIKE 21 suite, a bathymetric grid with incorrect vertical referencing directly affects hydrodynamic flux distribution, boundary conditions, and flow velocities. Moreover, Paul et al. (2025, p. 5) attempted to dilute the datum discrepancy by asserting that ‘the cited +2.82 m correction slightly differs from the actual reference value’. This careless mix-up of hydrographic datums — where a 0.18-m discrepancy is significant in low-gradient tidal areas — reflects their lack of understanding of datum control, which is crucial for bathymetric model calibration. Besides, they have clearly misused the mathematical sign ‘+’. As stated by Das et al. (2025), to make the NHO charts compatible, which use depths below MSL, 2.82 m must be *added* to all depth sounding values which are already negative.

2.3.3 Data merging issues

Paul et al. (2025) alleged that Das et al. (2025) misinterpreted the extent of NHO data used in Fig. 2a of Paul et al. (2024). However, Paul et al. (2024) did not specify the spatial limits or the manner in which NHO and GEBCO bathymetry were combined. In contrast, Das et al. (2025) performed a comparative assessment of depth contours from the NHO chart (unadjusted to chart datum) and the GEBCO-2021 grid to infer the spatial blending pattern, which they then depicted in their Fig. 2. It is therefore startling that Paul et al. (2025) presented, in their Fig. 4, the same integration pattern that Das et al. (2025) had already deduced — information that should have been clearly documented in their original work (Fig. 7). Notably, the zigzag alignment of the magenta dashed line in Paul et al.’s (2025) Fig. 4 closely matches the eastward longitudinal extent of the NHO-derived bathymetry demarcated by Das et al. (2025). Furthermore, Paul et al. (2025, p. 6) asserted in their Fig. 4 caption that ‘The blue dashed line shows the actual northern extent where bathymetric soundings are available; areas north of this line contain no depth data’, implying that Das et al. (2025) extrapolated the NHO Chart No. 301 beyond available data. This interpretation is once again misleading, as Das et al. (2025) clearly acknowledged in the final line of their Fig. 2 caption that ‘The soundings of the NHO Chart extend northward only up to 21°52’N’ — which precisely corresponds to the same northern limit of bathymetric soundings marked in Paul et al.’s (2025) Fig. 4.

2.3.4 Misconceptions about bathymetric surface generation

Paul et al. (2025, p. 5) questioned the bathymetric representation used by Das et al. (2025), alleging that contours were generated ‘in areas lacking echo-sounding data’. This remark reflects a basic misunderstanding of bathymetric surface construction from discrete depth soundings. Bathymetric maps are not confined to the exact locations of sounding points. They are generated by interpolation to produce a continuous surface that reflects depth variability across the study area. Such interpolation, based on the spatial relationship among measured points, is a globally accepted geospatial practice in hydrographic and topographic mapping. Thus, Paul et al.’s (2025) criticism of ‘extrapolation’ or ‘interpolation beyond coverage’ is scientifically invalid. Das et al. (2025) generated continuous bathymetric surfaces from NHO Chart No. 301 using ‘Kriging interpolation in ArcGIS 10.8, which is a widely validated geostatistical method. Whereas the GEBCO v2021 surface grids are freely downloadable from <https://www.gebco.net>. After surface creation, clipping to the target region is a simple cartographic operation. Therefore, Paul et al.’s (2025) allegation arises from a conceptual misunderstanding of depth-surface modelling and lacks any technical merit.

2.3.5 Lack of cartographic referencing and misleading geographic claims

Paul et al. (2025, p. 5) mentioned various place and channel names without providing any cartographic context, for example: ‘above ST-3 on the Calchara [sic] River (also known as Mural Gang or Mridangabhanga Gang)...’. This absence of mapped references echoes a persistent limitation in Paul et al. (2024), where multiple geographic names are cited but never spatially located. In contrast, Das et al. (2025) included clearly annotated maps marking all referenced sites and channels, thereby enabling readers to follow the spatial narrative. Without such cartographic support, the readers unfamiliar with the intricate creek network of the Indian Sundarban can hardly be expected to comprehend the spatial context or geographic relevance of the locations discussed by Paul et al. (2024, 2025).

Fig. 8. Refutation of Paul et al.'s (2025) erroneous claim regarding the tidally active Gobadia Gang. (a) Survey of India Topographic Map No. 79C/05 (1:50,000; surveyed in 1968–69) showing the channel's active nature. (b) Google Earth image (05 January 2022), contemporaneous to the purported survey period of Paul et al. (2024), clearly depicting the Gobadia Gang as an active tidal channel, contradicting Paul et al.'s (2025) claim that it is 'silted-up'. Boxed areas correspond to enlarged views in (c) and (d). (c) Enlarged view of the winter-time high tide condition (05 January 2022), showing two sizable boats moving in opposite directions with visible surf, confirming navigability. (d) Enlarged view of the summer-time high tide condition (15 May 2024) showing multiple boats anchored at adjacent jetties, disproving Paul et al.'s (2025) assertion.

Crucially, the lack of spatial referencing in Paul et al. (2025) also created scope for misrepresentation of unfamiliar locations, leading to erroneous interpretations. For instance, they claimed that ‘in silted-up rivers such as the Gabadia [sic] Gang (about 170 m wide), depth contours as deep as 5 m were drawn despite the absence of any supporting sounding observations’ (p. 5). This claim is incorrect and misleading, as bathymetric surfaces were generated from field-measured depth soundings detailed earlier. More importantly, the Gobadia Gang is not a ‘silted-up’ course but an active tidal channel, as confirmed by historical topographical sheets and recent satellite images (Fig. 8).

2.4 Issues Related to Model setup and validation

2.4.1 Lack of empirical basis and unsupported parameter selection

The *Summary Reply*’s Section 2.4 presents a sequence of assertions that are either unsupported by empirical evidence, internally contradictory, or incompatible with the established principles of open-channel hydraulics and estuarine flow dynamics. Paul et al. (2025, p. 5) stated that their model parameters — drying depth (0.0005 m), flooding depth (0.05 m), horizontal eddy viscosity (0.28), and Coriolis factor — were ‘derived from MIKE Zero’s toolbox and verified against regional studies’. However, once again, no published study, supplementary data, or reference list is provided to justify these parameter selections or the claimed verification. The lack of regional validation and transparent documentation casts serious doubt on the empirical grounding of the modelling framework.

2.4.2 Misinterpretation and misuse of Manning’s roughness coefficient

The *Summary Reply* proceeds to address the issue of Manning’s roughness coefficient, where the authors acknowledge what they describe as a ‘typographical error’ (p. 6) in the published range of Manning’s ‘M’ values. According to Paul et al. (2025), the originally reported range ‘–0.58 to 56.14’ should have read ‘0.58–56.14 $m^{(1/3)}/s$,’ with the negative sign apparently being a mistaken substitute for a hyphen. This explanation is not only linguistically inaccurate but also scientifically indefensible. In the original article of Paul et al. (2024), the text in Section 2.3.4 states: ‘the roughness changes depending on the bathymetry of the regime from –0.58 $m^{(1/3)}/s$ to –56.14 $m^{(1/3)}/s$ ’. The explanation offered in the *Summary Reply* thus contradicts the syntax, numerical logic, and physical context of the original publication. The notion that the preposition ‘to’ can precede a hyphen is grammatically invalid, and the attempt to frame this as a casual typographical mistake probably addresses their conceptual misunderstanding. Beyond the textual inconsistencies, the physical implications of these values are problematic as well. In Das et al. (2025), references were made to Manning (1891) and other related articles, which clearly define that Manning’s ‘M’ — the inverse of Manning’s ‘n’ — ranges typically between 10 and 100 $m^{(1/3)}/s$, corresponding to ‘n’ values between 0.1 and 0.01 $s/m^{(1/3)}$. Applying the claimed ‘corrected’ range from the *Summary Reply*, 0.58 and 56.14 correspond respectively to ‘n’ values of 1.724 and 0.0178. The former represents an impossible magnitude of hydraulic resistance, while the latter corresponds to extremely smooth concrete or steel-lined conduits — conditions that do not occur in natural environments (Manning, 1891; Chow, 1959). These values are not only inconsistent with field-based observations but also incompatible with the morphodynamic variability of tidal estuaries. As emphasised in Das et al. (2025), the Manning formulation is inherently unsuitable for representing hydraulic resistance in tidal systems, as constantly changing bedforms, sediment suspension, and shear stress prevent the application of a single representative Manning’s value. Thus, Paul et al.’s (2025)

Summary Reply fails to resolve the methodological deficiencies related to Manning’s roughness coefficient, while introducing additional absurdities that further corrode the credibility of the modelling framework originally presented.

2.5 Issues related to the results

2.5.1 Misrepresentation of the Hugli and Sundarban estuarine systems

Paul et al. (2025, p. 6) stated that the Hugli and the Sundarban estuaries ‘differ fundamentally’, citing fluvial versus tidal dominance and differences in estuarine width. Tides propagate across regional hydrodynamic scales. Both the Hugli and its adjacent Sundarban rivers, located within the same latitudinal and climatic zone, are subjected to similar tidal forcing. To dismiss latitudinal comparison on the grounds of ‘fundamental’ differences ignores this process-based context. The mean local sea level of the Hugli stays 0.18 m (at Sagar, 0 km from sea) to 0.48 m (at Diamond Harbour, 72 km from sea) above MSL due to the freshets it receives (SoI, 2024). This only means that the MSL in the tide diagram of Paul et al. (2025: Fig. 3) should have been higher compared to the Hugli (cf. Fig. 4 of Das et al., 2025). This clearly brings out Paul et al.’s (2024) problem in normalising tide gauge data to MSL.

2.5.2 Invalid model validation through data recycling

Paul et al. (2025, p. 6) defended the remarkably close match between simulated and observed water levels by stating that they used a ‘resubstitution validation approach’, where the same boundary data served both calibration and validation. This is effectively a bootstrapping loop — feeding the model with its input data, allowing it to predict outcomes from the same dataset, and then using those predictions to claim validation success. In short, their model simply ‘learned’ what it was already given. Under such an arrangement, a high degree of similarity between observed and simulated values is inevitable, but meaningless. The apparent ‘strong agreement’ is not a demonstration of the model’s predictive capacity, but it is merely a reflection of data recycling. In Paul et al. (2024), there is no independent test of model generalisation, and no assurance that the model can replicate real-world conditions beyond its limited training dataset. The model’s outputs, therefore, represent the confirmation of its own input rather than the validation of its performance.

3. Conclusion

In sync with Das et al. (2025), this rebuttal identifies and elaborates on six major issues in the *Summary Reply* of Paul et al. (2025). *First*, the descriptions of tidal data collection using crude bamboo culms, inadequate manpower, dubious logistical setup, and incomplete datasets reveal a fundamental lack of scientific credibility. The inconsistencies in recording precise tidal variations for 15 consecutive days at seven remote stations, combined with 13% missing data, point toward serious deficiencies in field design and execution. *Second*, their handling of tidal referencing, MSL adjustment, and bathymetric correction remains logically indefensible. The confused interpretation of vertical datums and erratic merging of the low-resolution NHO and GEBCO datasets indicate a basic misunderstanding of datum control, vertical referencing, and bathymetric surface construction. *Third*, Paul et al. (2025) failed to rectify the conceptual and technical lapses in the hydrodynamic modelling framework. The misuse of Manning’s roughness coefficient, absence of empirical calibration, and reliance on data recycling for model validation highlight

the lack of understanding of estuarine hydraulics and the unreliability of the simulated results. *Fourth*, Paul et al. (2025) admitted that conventional surveying was ‘unfeasible’, and instead referenced their tidal data to MSL using a model-based approach, which they acknowledged as ‘less precise’. This means the vertical referencing relied on model outputs rather than geodetic control. Moreover, by using separate lowest modelled water levels for each station, they disregarded the requirement of a uniform vertical datum for comparative tidal analysis in the interconnected estuaries. This explains why the LLW levels across all stations reported by Paul et al. (2024) stayed above the MSL during the neaps, as they were sourced from unrealistic tidal readings that were never reconciled with the regional bathymetry. *Fifth*, Paul et al. (2025) did not address a major cartographic issue pointed out by Das et al. (2025) as their 2024 figures used varying data intervals and colour legends across panels for the same parameters, making the comparisons infeasible. *Sixth*, the inconsistencies in Paul et al.’s (2024) model validation and tidal dynamics analyses have only deepened through the rhetorical defence of Paul et al. (2025), suggesting an effort to obscure their own methodological flaws rather than addressing the scientific discrepancies identified in Das et al. (2025). The recurrent usage of the terms ‘misunderstanding’, ‘robust’, ‘rigorous’ etc., in Paul et al. (2025) exposes the authors’ contrived effort to rationalise data manipulation under the guise of scientific diligence.

Thus, Paul et al.’s (2025) *Summary Reply* appears to be an attempt to legitimise methodologically weak and empirically unsound claims while evading the substantive research inquiries raised by Das et al. (2025). By avoiding to address these critical arguments, Paul et al. (2025) reinforced our earlier assertion (Das et al., 2025) that Paul et al.’s (2024) tidal observations were unreliable and unsuitable for use in a scientific analysis. Their *Summary Reply* should not be viewed as a legitimate clarification, but rather as a post-hoc explanation that underscores the methodological fragility of Paul et al. (2024). In fact, Paul et al. (2025) further established the unsoundness of Paul et al.’s (2024) findings. We feel that retraction of the original work should be seriously considered for the benefit of future research on tidal hydrodynamics of the Indian Sundarban.

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